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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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Teaching with Heart: Building Strong Connections in Our Community Schools

Bebeche D. Pagalan, LPT

Teacher

Himaya Elementary School

El Salvador City Division, Misamis Oriental, Philippines

In our busy community, where every street and person have a unique story, schools are very important. They are more than just buildings; they are places where future leaders and caring individuals grow up. "Teaching with Heart" means understanding and caring for each learner, not just in their studies but also in their feelings. According to Smith (2023), when teachers focus on students' emotions and involve the community, it has a positive and lasting effect on their lives.

In our local schools, teachers who "Teach with Heart" build strong relationships with their learners. They make sure every child feels important and understood. This approach helps learners do better in school and teaches them to be kind and strong, which are important skills for life (Johnson, 2022). By focusing on these values, our teachers inspire and support learners, helping them to make positive contributions to our community and beyond. "Teaching with Heart" also means that teachers are part of the community. They are not just teaching from a book but also connecting with learners on a personal level. This helps students feel safe and valued in the classroom. When learners know their teachers care about them, they are more excited to learn. They enjoy learning more and take their lessons seriously. This positive environment helps students become better learners and better people. The benefits of "Teaching with Heart" go beyond the classroom. Students bring what they learn into their homes and the community. They learn to be kind, understanding, and to work well with others. This makes our community a better place for everyone. Students who feel cared for are more likely to help others and be good citizens. They develop a sense of responsibility and a desire to make the world a better place.

Emotional intelligence is a big part of "Teaching with Heart." Teachers who understand their students' feelings can better meet their needs and create a good learning environment. By recognizing and supporting students' emotions, teachers help build their confidence and self-esteem. This support encourages students to try new things, explore new ideas, and engage more fully in their education.

A classroom where "Teaching with Heart" is practiced is one where students feel empowered to express themselves and take charge of their learning. Teachers who adopt this approach create a positive and inclusive learning environment. They use teaching methods that cater to different learning styles and encourage active participation. This inclusivity ensures that all students, no matter their background or abilities, have the chance to succeed.

The long-term benefits of "Teaching with Heart" are significant. Students who feel supported and valued are more likely to develop a lifelong love of learning. They are also

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more likely to pursue higher education and reach their full potential. Moreover, the skills and values taught by caring teachers prepare students to handle the challenges of adult life. They learn to communicate effectively, solve problems creatively, and work well with others. Several examples show the power of "Teaching with Heart." For instance, a middle school in our community started a program focused on building strong teacher-student relationships. The results were amazing: students' grades improved, fewer students missed school, and there was a big increase in positive behavior. Teachers felt more connected to their students and more satisfied with their jobs. This example shows how compassionate teaching can bring about positive change.

In conclusion, "Teaching with Heart" is about more than just teaching. It is about creating strong, supportive relationships and making our community stronger. By understanding and caring for each student, our teachers are helping to build a brighter future for everyone. The impact of this approach extends beyond the classroom, leading to a more caring and connected society. As more educators embrace "Teaching with Heart," they shape not only the minds but also the hearts of the next generation, building a world where empathy, understanding, and cooperation are key.

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